

USE OF THE “GREEN GARDEN PROJECT” FOR THE PURPOSE OF GREENING THE ENVIRONMENT IN PROVIDING ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION TO STUDENTS THROUGH CONSERVATION AND RESPECT FOR NATURE

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses the current issue, namely, the importance of educating students in the protection and respect of nature through the national technology project “green gardens”, and the importance of preserving the purity of the atmosphere as an important resource for creating a healthy environment in the future.

KEYWORDS: Ecological education, ecological education, “green garden” “green space” ecological worldview, atmospheric air, public health, nature protection.

INTRODUCTION: The great attention paid to environmental education of students in our country through the preservation and respect of nature, the development of new methodological approaches to ensuring the interaction and integrative connection of the ecological worldview with national and universal values. 2025 was named the “Year of Environmental Protection and the “Green” Economy”. It is necessary to plant trees within the framework of the “Green Space” project not for their name, but “for our lives, for the cleanliness of our lungs, because we need it for ourselves, our society, and our health,” said the President of Uzbekistan. Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Therefore, improving the didactic support of technologies for increasing the efficiency of environmental education of students through the preservation and respect of nature is of great importance. As our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted: “The effectiveness of the reforms being carried out in our country today directly depends, first of all, on expanding the ranks of young cadres with high spirituality, independent thinking, capable of taking responsibility for the fate and prospects of our Motherland.” After Uzbekistan gained independence, serious attention was paid to the issues of environmental education and nature protection through the preservation and respect of nature for students, and several laws and decrees were promulgated, and measures were taken to implement them. The following decrees and laws can be cited as examples in this regard.

The Decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Nature Protection” of December 9, 1992, “On Water and Water Use” of May 6, 1993, “On Subsoil Resources” of September 22, 1994, “On Air Protection” of December 27, 1996, “On the Protection of the Animal World and Its Rational Use” and “On the Protection of the Plant World and Its Rational Use” of December 26, 1997, as well as a number of other laws and decrees issued in this regard are among them. This research work will to a certain extent serve to ensure the implementation of the tasks set out in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, Resolution No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, Resolution No. 434 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 2019 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, and other regulatory legal acts related to this activity.

The Strategy for the Preservation of Biodiversity in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2028, the implementation of the national project "Green Space" initiated by our President, is significant in that it serves such noble and human values. Among them, a number of traditions aimed at ensuring the harmony of man and nature still accompany our lives. For example, when a child is born in a family, with good intentions, grandfathers and fathers plant a tree in his honor, creating both sustenance and beauty for the world. As a powerful sanitizer, the green surface of trees and shrubs absorbs carbon dioxide and releases oxygen necessary for human life. Trees, like all living things, have their own source of energy.

Because people enjoy the aroma emanating from trees and their mood improves. The nationwide project "Green Space" being implemented in our country is an important factor in ensuring the continuity of such noble values and achieving sustainable development. Within the framework of this ecological project, which has become a tradition at the initiative of our President, it is planned to plant 200 million tree and shrub seedlings annually, thereby increasing the green areas of our country from the current 8 percent to 30 percent. As our President noted, the national project "Green Space" is not a one-year event. It is also worth recognizing that this noble initiative, which is being implemented with tomorrow in mind, is highly appreciated by many international organizations. All information in this regard is provided in the model of providing students with environmental education through the preservation and respect of nature.

Today's reforms in the field of education in the newly developing Republic of Uzbekistan are changing the practical forms, methods and means of providing students with environmental education through the preservation and respect of nature in accordance with the requirements of the times. Communication with nature is of great importance in the moral development of a person. Love for Mother Nature, preservation and protection of all its wealth are an impetus for the formation of ecological concepts.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, nature conservation has always been relevant. Developing ecological education for the growing younger generation through the preservation and respect of nature is a fascinating and attractive way to preserve, protect and appreciate nature and flora, and how important the work carried out to develop environmental protection is for society and for people. Therefore, providing students with ecological education through the preservation and respect of nature is an important and urgent issue.

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